

Survey 2026, the Educational and Math History Part

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Abstract

This paper deals with teaching and learning modern Linear Algebra and it elaborates on our most urgent task in Mathematics as a whole, and more specifically, in how to teach Linear Algebra to freshmen today. To be effective, it is time now to create and propagate modern Matrix Theory and Matrix Computation based Syllabi. We introduce suitable examples of first year Linear Algebra courses, including my own comprehensive Lesson Plans. We expose and discuss them.

To prepare our post-Covid students properly, we need to use interactive teaching methods and inversely taught syllabi now.

My Lesson Plans are slowly creating a grass-roots fire among students and catching instructors as well.

My Lesson Plan course follows the Teaching Principles of Jean Piaget from 80 years ago who established that we only learn deeply and retain what we need to understand, and not what we are taught in order to pass a test or to graduate.

My modern elementary Linear Algebra course has been designed and class tested. It relies only on three mathematical principles.

First the Row Echelon Form Reduction teaches us of the value of pivot searches.

Then Krylov Vector Iteration allows us to look inside intrinsic matrix qualities such as matrix eigenvectors and eigenvalues.

Both of these rely on Riesz's Theorem on Matrix Representations of Linear Functions in varying vector space bases.

Early on, my students build their own basic software codes for essential tasks in modern Linear Algebra. They will improve them and adapt them continually as the course progresses. They will learn throughout the course why and how to use computer computations rather than computing by hand.

Matrices are used everywhere in today's world, in the internet, in our cell-phone and computer worlds, and in Engineering, AI, Medicine, Shipping, Traveling, Banking, and so forth.

The proposed course achieves deep learning in students of inversely taught classrooms.

Keywords : math history, Linear Algebra, interactive teaching, inverse classroom methods, math education, lesson plans, elementary Linear Algebra, elementary Matrix Computations, Linear Algebra syllabi, deep learning, Piaget Principle, Semmelweis Syndrome, meta-mathematics

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Talk Slides at

<https://webhome.auburn.edu/~uhligfd/Survey2026Edupart.pdf>

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0 : *A Detour* : A Foreword of Sorts, on the Genesis of the Matrix Field of Values Discovery trail from 1907 to 1918

I started my current cluster of papers in the early 2020s by investigating the early appearances of the concept behind, and the actual term of "Matrix Fields of Values" (FOV), in the math literature. This was then just an idle pastime that lead me to results in six or seven distinct mathematical areas. I solved century or decade old fundamental science problems tat were open and abandoned. But back to and start with the FoV genesis now :

Otto Toeplitz and Felix Hausdorff were the first mathematicians to conceive of and introduce this term into the mathematical literature.

Toeplitz approached this topic at the Berlin Academy and coined the term "Wertbereich" (note: no plural 'e') in his first invited talk in front of the Academy in 1901/1902 for his dissertaion there, published as such in 1910 [27]. The mathematical language and papers at the time had no such terms. Toeplitz developed matrix and convexity computational ideas to plot the boundary curve of that new mathematical 'item', the 'Field of Values', concretely.

Another approach came from the then popular studies of Operator Polynomials in Linear Functions in infinite dimensional Normed Vector Spaces. These eventually morphed into the beginnings of Functional Analysis in the middle years of the 1900s.

Felix Hausdorff, on the other hand, had studied these Banach Space ideas and he studied the FoV concepts as special constructions involving n dimensional Vector Sets under Linear Transformations and this lead him to eventually understand the convexity of the FOV for all square matrices [14] in 1918/1919.

The mathematics that surround the *historic matrix Field of Values genesis* from the early 1900s are well explained by Leopold Féjer [9] and by Isabelle Bensi-mon and Kalin Kostadinov in [5].

Henry Minkowski's convex body theorem and proof from around 1900 for $n = 2$ is equally important for understanding the roots of the Matrix Fields of Values, see the survey [6] by Daniel Comeaux.

The operator convexity results were - theoretically - applied in the early 1900s to the mapping of vectors in \mathbb{R}^n to their images on the Field of Values boundary. The field of values boundary points were then to be 'obtained' from the extreme eigenvalue eigenvectors x of A after evaluating the Rayleigh quotient - theoretically again - $x^* A x / x^* x \in \mathbb{R}$, - in the 2-D range plane, acting as our common drawing plane. Long before Computers and actual Computations of matrix eigenvalues were possible.

Here is a Mathematische Zeitschrift article [28] of excerpts from Felix Hausdorff's analysis from that time, copied from the German original of 1910.

Herr Toeplitz hat in dieser Zeitschrift kürzlich gezeigt¹⁾, daß der Wertvorrat W einer Bilinearform, als Punktmenge in der komplexen Zahlenebene, außen von einer konvexen Kurve begrenzt ist, aber die Frage offen gelassen, ob er das ganze Innere dieser Kurve erfüllt. Es ist nun sehr einfach zu zeigen, daß diese Frage zu bejahen, nämlich W selbst eine konvexe Menge ist.

Wenn C und C^ eine n -reihige Matrix und ihre begleitende (konjugiert-transponierte) Matrix bedeuten, so sind durch*

$$A = 1/2(C + C^*), \quad B = 1/2i(C - C^*)$$

oder umgekehrt

$$C = A + iB, \quad C^* = A - iB$$

zwei Hermitesche Matrizen A, B , die Komponenten von C , definiert. Eine lineare Substitution (nichtverschwindender Determinante) mit der Matrix P , die C in $C = PCP^$ überführt, führt gleichzeitig C^* in C^* und die Komponenten A, B in die Komponenten A, B über.*

Der Wertvorrat W von C ist, nach Herrn Toeplitz, die Menge der komplexen Zahlen w , welche die Form

¹⁾ O. Toeplitz, Das algebraische Analogon zu einem Satze von Fejér, Math. Zeitschrift 2 (1918), S. 187–197.

$$C(x, \bar{x}) = \sum_{\alpha, \beta} c_{\alpha\beta} x_{\alpha} \bar{x}_{\beta} = w$$

durchläuft, wenn die komplexen Veränderlichen x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n der Bedingung

$$(1) \quad E(x, \bar{x}) = \sum_{\alpha} a_{\alpha} a_{\alpha} \bar{x}_{\alpha} = 1, \text{ i.e. } \text{norm}(x)_2 = 2 \text{ für die Frobenius 2-norm.}$$

unterworfen werden. Zerlegen wir C in seine Komponenten, so ist W die Menge der reellen Wertpaare (u, v) oder der Punkte mit rechtwinkligen Koordinaten u, v , die ein Paar Hermitescher Formen

$$A(x, \bar{x}) = u, \quad B(x, \bar{x}) = v$$

unter der Bedingung (1) durchläuft.

Durch eine unitäre Substitution ($PP^* = E$), die offenbar den Wertvorrat von C nicht ändert, können wir die Hermitesche Matrix A in eine Diagonalmatrix überführen oder also von vornherein

$$A(x, \bar{x}) = \sum_{\alpha} a_{\alpha} x_{\alpha} \bar{x}_{\alpha}$$

als Diagonalform mit den Eigenwerten a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n annehmen. Sei dann u_0 ein Wert, den $A(x, \bar{x})$ unter der Bedingung (1) annimmt, der also zwischen dem kleinsten und größten Eigenwert liegt; geometrisch gesprochen: die zur v -Achse parallele Gerade $u = u_0$ schneide die Menge W .

Es kommt nun einfach darauf an, zu zeigen, daß die Menge M der Wertsysteme $x := (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, für die gleichzeitig

$$A(x, \bar{x}), \quad E(x, \bar{x}) = 1$$

gilt, zusammenhängend ist.

(Eingegangen am 28. November 1918.)

These historical works have all laid the FoV concepts and groundwork for Charlie Johnson's practical computational method for drawing of the Field of Values boundary curve in [17]. Johnson's method depends on effective and accurate matrix eigen-computations that had become available in Matrix Numerical Analysis by using John G. F. Francis' QR algorithm [10, 11, 13] and reliable LAPACK codes and software in the mid 1970s, 50 Years ago.

300 years or more years ago, the relation between the coefficients of various short power series such as Taylor Series, Fourier Series, or algebraic polynomials were scrutinized for their function or mapping properties.

Which truncated leading power series snippets would transfer compact sets in the domain into compact sets in their range space. Such *fundamental questions of Compactness, Closedness and Convexity* seem of great import in much of Mathematics. And these concepts are all *intertwined* since Descartes' or Cardano's times, and possibly much earlier, from Aristotle and Archimedes, and their predecessors, and followers, in antiquity and into modern times, - all around the globe.

They involved concepts in *Algebra and Geometry, Analysis and Topology*, and *Number Theory*. Eventually nascent *Matrix Theory* was involved after Seki, Leibniz, Cauchy, Gauss, Sylvester, Weierstrass and many others from 1600 through the 1800s. And today *Matrix Theory, Matrix Computations* and *Matrix Applications* are still being developed further and have had *many uses* in the *expanding engineering work* of the beginning *Industrial Revolution* from the mid 1700s and 1800s in Europe. And likewise in our rapid Engineering advances of the 2000s; and so forth, today and tomorrow – for our *ever increasing human needs*.

These developments lead mathematicians first to the notions of *compact sets* and their preservation under *continuous maps*, then to the concept of *convexity* and the desire to preserve some properties under 'power series snippet mappings'. If a set lay in certain ways in the domain, what was the smallest set in the range space that would contain all snippet images and so forth.

The Toeplitz [28] and Hausdorff [14] results seem remote now for my research cluster, but they paved the way for our *modern numerical Fields of Values studies* and their use in applications from the 1960s through today.

How to actually *compute the Field of Values boundary curve numerically* was introduced and studied by Charlie Johnson [16, 17] and others only after the *invention of computers* and the development of *mathematical software* from the 1940s into the 1970s.

My cluster results from the early 2020s are all *interconnected* and *intertwined*, forwards and backwards, and crossways and sideways with much of our *Mathematical History*. When trying to draw the directed edge implication graph of my research cluster on paper, I found out that the minimal directed graph dimension requires at least three or four dimensions, since one or two dimensional dimensions drawings will clearly not suffice.

My recent research cluster results all hinge on newly extended versions of *Matrix Theory* and *Matrix Computations*, developed by the Author and helped along by many others.

The theory behind our new *computational matrix algorithm* is seemingly elementary, some of it is rather common and historical. It uses the *concept of invariant subspaces* for Matlab's `eig` computed 'eigenvectors' or Krylov Vector Iterations of one *flow matrix* $B(t_a)$ to find the *coarsest simultaneous block structure* for all flow matrices $B(t_b)$ with $t_a \neq t_b$ combinatoriely from a user set Threshold. The combined method block-diagonalizes any given matrix flow $A(t)$, or any given static matrix A – as finely as possible, if at all.

Our intended aim in [38] was to discover *unitarily diagonal-block decomposable matrices* and *matrix flows* quickly and *fast and accurate* enough for real world use *in real-time* from *time-varying sensor data*.

The (unitary) *block-decomposition of matrix flows or single square matrices* has not been resolved by algebraic means *in 100 + years* and this has possibly never been tried before, because – I believe – there *existed no algebraic way or ideas to start from* – before *the advent of computers and Matrix based software*.

Instead, *our new way* of testing and *establishing decomposability* of a *Matrix* or *Matrix flow* hinges entirely on new *numerical algorithms* that decide the issue depending on the *lay of the near zero entries* and of the *sizable ones* in the *associated hermitean Johnson matrix flow*

$$\mathcal{F}(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K \quad (\text{XXX})$$

for $0 \leq t \leq 2\pi$.

Compare the sketch by von Neumann and Paul Wigner [22, p.469] with our logical 0-1 computational and combinatorial output in [38], Figures 1 through 5 on pages 536 through 541 for matrices with no repeated eigenvalues, and in [38] and Figure 6 on p. 542 for matrices with sizable Jordan blocks or with repeated eigenvalues.

As a 'classical' *algebraic proof* of our result has *never been attempted*, we dare to claim that *an algorithmic proof* was actually impossible *before the advent of computers* and a deeper understanding of *matrix flows* such as the *hermitean Johnson flow* $\mathcal{F}(t)$ and the *predictive qualities and accuracy of Zhang Neural Networks*, as brought to light recently in ZNN [43] or AZNN [41].

Albert Einstein shunned this fundamental Quantum Theory problem and rather worked on relativity.

Niels Bohr's group wanted to understand *eigencurve crossings* and their *relation to the matrix block-decomposability of matrices*, see the exploratory plot by von Neumann and Paul Wigner [22, p. 469] from 1929.

But neither succeeded in solidifying the foundations of Quantum Theory and Quantum Chemistry.

Eigencurve crossing studies for the still un-resolved block-diagonalization problem would begin anew with Charlie Johnson's practical method [17] for constructing the FOV *boundary curve* in the 1970s and pick up again in the 1990s in Luca Dieci et al.'s papers [7], [8] and in many other papers of Luca's research group, and by others; and in Loisel and Maxwell's paper [20], and in some of my eigencurve papers [32], Chapter 9.1, [36], [37], [38], [44], e. g. .

This continued until around 2020, when several small partial results (maybe 10 to 15 %) of the *block-decomposition problem* had been solved, but no complete classification had been found and the century old *deep fundamental Quantum problems* of this introductory write-up were still open in 2023, until [38] appeared in print.

My finally successful *classification* of unitary *block-decompositions* [38] for both, general matrix flows and static matrices, was ultimately inspired by *Yunong Zhang's parameter-varying Neural Networks* that date back to his doctoral thesis [45] of 2001.

Why spent several pages on complicated mathematical results in the introduction to a Math education paper on structuring and teaching the *first Linear Algebra Course in a modern way*.

The reason being : all our Electronic Computers are based at their very lowest, the bottom basic level, entirely on *Matrix and Vector Operations*; in all of our search engines ...

All of our internet bankings, of our phoning operations, of our podcast streaming etc. are ultimately *depending on Matrices and Vector Spaces* and on *our coding and understanding thereof*.

Unfortunately (or luckily), the 'classically taught' first Linear Algebra courses are the most hated Math courses overall. That sad fact needs to be *remedied*.

Most of our early Linear Algebra courses are totally out of sync with after-Covid times where students had to learn quickly, by themselves or in spontaneous 'Zoom' groups, what the majority of our standard Linear Algebra courses then did not teach and still do not teach today.

These 'classic' courses still rather rehash the highlights of the 18th and 19th century as their final 'summit' topics.

See the two before 1930 and after 1930 Linear Algebra subjects lists in the APPENDIX, on p. 28 and p. 29 and compare.

But *help is already on the way* in the form of *embedded grass-root advice* for student use in all my seven Lesson Plans.

This '*disconnect*' between *our modern needs* and the *classical discredited course contents* is the subject of this *Math Education paper*.

Trying to remedy and help all actors here, there have been many attempts to improve this situation, other than my comprehensive Lesson Plans. Historically, the textbook of Hans Schneider and Phillip Barker [24] of 1968 with its title *Matrices and Linear Algebra* were the earliest attempt here to put matrices at the front of any early Linear Algebra class.

At that time there were efforts by the Linear Algebra group at the Bureau of Standards in Washington DC to start a Linear Algebra journal that eventually was started under the Title "Linear Algebra and its Applications" (LAA) in 1973 at the insistence of Elsevier, instead of "Matrices and their Applications" as Hans had suggested.

More modern and matrix oriented are the recent efforts by David Austin [2] in his teaching by subject clusters. His interactive website asks students to choose between its 30+ subject worksheets and pass a test after they feel confident of

what they have learned. At first they are asked to choose 2 subsections of the whole set and then, according to their understandings and errors in the chosen subject areas, the interactive web-book asks them to repeat or it 'passes' them after successfully finishing one or two additional subject tests. David and his GTAs monitor the progress and after successfully passing 12 subject tests satisfactorily, they have to sit through an oral exam on the material to get a one semester class credit. The whole course is designed for a full year course. On exit and again after one more year, David and his crew sends them a questionnaire on Linear Algebra, asking about the usefulness of the subject matter in their further studies and also for their suggestions.

This is the only comprehensive text-book that I know of. It is very labor intensive, however, for David and his Crew, but it is very successful in educating students in Modern Matrix Ways.

The text-books of Sheldon Axler [3] and Gilbert Strang [25] also offer a modern matrix approach, but both invariably veer off into teaching the old stuff from Cauchy's time and minimal or characteristic polynomials of square matrix and their dead-born root computations. A modern reoccurrence of Semmelweis Syndrome, by honoring how we were all taught for decades, and our teachers and their teachers were, for centuries before.

We also recommend to read [1] on these subjects of what to teach and how to teach Linear Algebra.

Preamble II

In East Asia's Taiwan and South Korea in 2014, I gave two separate talks at WONRA and ILAS Meetings on the FOV and Math Computations' history and on my current cluster of results in Matrix Theory and Matrix Computations from a new extraordinary rich cluster of Mathematical Research papers.

The Math Ed paper below addresses our elementary Linear Algebra teachings and deals with the globe-wide problem of "teaching for the test", mostly in 'top-down' lecturing.

Unfortunately we are generally not conveying Linear Algebra through Interactive Teaching Methods, nor introducing Modern Matrix Theory and Matrix Computational Methods to our beginning students.

But Help is already on its way ...

Overcoming this dilemma is the most urgent task
in all of Mathematics

Today

Are there *any problems* in our Linear Algebra teaching, or teachings ?

In subjects taught, or ... where are our problems – if any ?

In Linear Algebra and Matrix Theory, what is wrong ?

Teaching and/or Research wise ?

What needs to be done immediately ?

We must modernize our early College syllabi in Linear Algebra and enliven this area of Mathematics that helps us all so extraordinarily in our daily cell-phone and internet based lives, and in our AI and engineering advances.

How do we, how do you mostly teach the beginners' linear algebra classes today?

Which *subjects* do we, you, and I teach ?

Using modern Matrix Theory based ideas *or* from a classical and algebraic standpoint ?

Top-down taught *or* taught interactively ?

These are *our most urgent questions* today,
in All of Mathematics

1 : Math Education today, or *the Necessity of Modernizing the First Linear Algebra Course via coherent Matrix Theory Based Lesson Plans*

Based on [44], this section looks at how and what is standardly taught in our first College or University Linear Algebra courses in the US, in Europe, in the Americas, in Africa, and in Asia – and around the globe.

Historically speaking, Linear Algebra has had *two periods of great expansions*.

One was in the 19th century and another is going on right now, as this area of mathematics has gained great importance and is being rejuvenated by deep *changes in the subject matter and in our understandings* thereof since the 1950s, with the *advent of electronic computers*.

With *Covid*, we have switched to mostly *on-line teaching* and *little thought* about the consequences.

To get a feel for what is going on globe-wide, search any university website for Linear Algebra video resources and you will find that the majority of our subject's first College courses are given in 'Vorlesungs' style, 'top-down', with *little red dots running around pages*, on a screen or handy — with the instructor droning on, as she or he *reads out aloud* to the class or section, – on-line or off.

Here the English word of 'lecture' is replaced by its German equivalent "Vorlesung" which literally means a 'reading' from a script or a book – or (with a *little red dot flickering* across the screen) – from a 'canned' internet site.

The Vorlesungs-'readers' now are mostly young Ph. Ds. or postdocs, or young faculty, who most often *lecture top-down on-line*, with *few interactive or inverse methods of teaching or learning* Linear Algebra. Living in the current "publish or perish" times.

We have succumbed to the *Semmelweis Syndrome*, unknowingly – and *knowing no better way than to teach as they were taught ...* , and how we were most likely taught ourselves, *decades and centuries ago*, 'honoring our teachers'

[Look up 'Ignaz Semmelweis' who advocated hand-washing at childbirth to reduce infections and deaths at the two separate gynecological wards, one lead by midwives and the other by medical research gynecologists, at the Charité in Berlin around 1800. He could not convince his medical colleagues to wash their hands, because this was not mandated in their educational and professional canons, or how they were taught.]

What could have been wrong with this approach then?

About 5 times the childbirth and mothers' deaths occurred in the *medical doctors lead gynecology ward* than in the *midwives one*.

This attitude is reflected in our *glaring 'defect'* in most *math educational systems* today and nearly world wide : Most of us teach, how we were taught and thereby honor one of the Mosaic Ten Commandments, *to honor one's parents*, or teachers.

But we forget the other Commandment, namely *not to kill*, which we do to our students' growth in their wish to learn in the almost ubiquitous on-line, top-down Linear Algebra classes, delivered on-line or by in-class lecturing.

This makes the *first Linear Algebra course* the *most hated course* of all College Math courses.

This *defect* has to be *overcome quickly, like yesterday* in our early *Linear Algebra* courses; assuming that we want to give our first year *elementary Linear Algebra* students the *value education* that they *deserve, want, and need* today.

Linear Algebra now requires *alternate methods of teaching, modified subject lists* and *modern subject development methods* that are congruent with the ubiquitous modern uses of *Matrix Theory* and *Matrix Computations*.

Can we teach Linear Algebra in a new way?

What would that new way be?

Will 'any new way' succeed to *modernize our first Linear Algebra course* soon enough and teach our students the *same subject matter*, but in a *modern, useful, and usable way*?

We must *adopt different ways to teach*.

The *times are ripe for on-line and interactive teaching*.

Here is our chance to veer off from our near universal practice of *learning* and thereby *teaching for a test*.

This has been the standard teaching practice for decades in US schools. And *since Pisa* it has *sadly* become the *global teaching norm* abroad as well.

The century old *Piaget principle* on how humans of all ages *learn deeply*, stipulates clearly that we *learn best* when we *want to learn* and *need to learn* for *our own enjoyment* and for *our own personal mental growth*.

Google 'Jean Piaget'. Jean lived and worked in Switzerland all of his life and do read some of his readily available books and talks.

Here, in elementary *Inversely Taught Classes* on Linear Algebra is our *chance to set this abomination right*. For one :

My *Lesson Plans* will generate *True Learning* in our students.

This approach will set them free to use their acquired skills in many other professions by learning about the *Art of Mathematics* – without becoming Mathematicians themselves, unless they want to.

In our first Linear Algebra courses around the globe today, there are clearly around 20 to 100 (\pm) times more students than 'teachers'.

Now our students are hurt by most of us *inadvertently*, as we are overwhelmingly still teaching the achievements of the 1800s through the early 2000s as our *Linear Algebra* courses' *highlights*.

And our students suffer the most by our unfair and inadequate teaching methods (top-down lecturing, with centuries old 'highlights' and 'long discredited' nonsense).

Thus it is appropriate to engage our students directly and help them to rid themselves of this curse and its stifling grip on their inadequate teachings.

And hopefully change their College teachers likewise. But how done ?

In East Asia and the US last summer (2024) I learnt that both *teachers* and their elementary Linear Algebra course *students* are becoming well aware of my *modern Lesson Plans*, of their coherence and complete way to treat *all standard subjects anew*, but without any *long discarded ballast* of centuries ago. That made me very glad.

I call this happening a world wide "**grass-roots fire**" that is fueled by the Post-Covid students themselves, 'a fire' that will change the whole way in which we teach elementary Linear Algebra Courses from now on and **transform** them, see [32]. We must change them into *Modern Matrix* and *Modern Matrix Computations* courses, – in hopefully very few years.

My Lesson Plans create *critical thinkers, doers and citizens* –
in Piaget's way.

I have seen this transformation in many of my *Interactively Taught Classes*. Regularly my graduating students would bring their parents to my office on Graduation Day, to see me. Those students whom I had given their last C or C- for their inadequate learning efforts in my class.

Thereafter they had become all As or Bs students, because *they had learnt to think and work by and for themselves*. Therefore :

*'Vorlesungs' style top-down lecturing,
even on-line, is clearly out.*

Matrix Theory can nowadays best be taught via *Interactive Teaching and Learning about Matrices*.

Ideally I can envision an *on-line source of Lessons* that *students read and study first at home*, then *come to class to discuss and deepen each Lesson's* contents.

With the teacher at hand, *studying in small groups* of 3 to 5 or 6 to 12 or 25 students in each group; working on several black- or white-boards, life or on-line, in *one classroom* on campus, or on *Zoom*.

A *holistic analysis diagram* of our tasks in any first Linear Algebra course was given earlier in [44] and studied in several previous Linear Algebra education workshops around the globe.

Next we expand and explain the *holistic process* in 3 diagrams :

An attempt at a *basic holistic map* of the *spiderweb of forces* that govern our efforts to learn and to teach Mathematics today in 2026.

At its center : *the actors, you and I*

Learners and Teachers; *dwellers all, in time and space* [4] .

An attempt at a basic holistic map of the *spiderweb of forces* that govern our efforts to learn and teach *Mathematics* today in 2026.

At its center : the actors, *you and I* .
Learners and teachers; all combined .

[**How ? What ? When ? Why ?**]

The "Why"s, or our personal motivations and aims with teaching.

The "What" to teach, and the "When" to teach "What" and how.

[**How ? What ? When ? Why ?**]

The Pedagogy for today's students, given our current Awareness and the need to Teach Interactively, with modern Matrix Computational Thoughts and modern Matrix Methods.

The [**How ? What ? When ? Why ?**]

All explained in one holistic diagram

Our *Linear Algebra Teaching Dilemma* today is presented clearly on the *two 'diagonal' arrow pairs* of the holistic diagrams above.

Driven by the desire to *relieve the students' problems* depicted there, my *set of Lesson Plans* has been developed specifically for *Interactive Teaching* and for *Inverse Teaching Methods* in a *coherent and comprehensive Matrix based Way*.

The Lesson Plans are freely available for all at

<https://la-education.oucreate.com/teaching-resources/lesson-plans/franks-lesson-plans/>.

The inverse teaching approach generally works wonders.

Usually my students become coaches and tutors after a few weeks for students in parallel elementary Linear Algebra classes that are taught in classical subjects textbook style, on-line or off.

A student income source and an early teaching experience.

The *Lesson Plans* point to *what we teach* our students from the *historic development of Mathematics* today.

Choosing between centuries old 'stuff' or 'modern' concepts.

This is affected by the *students' mental maturity level* – and by *our own awareness level* as instructors. As both, mathematicians and listening teachers.

My *Lesson Plans* are designed to *help students and teacher to understand and appreciate the subjects* of our *classical algebraic first Linear Algebra curriculum* intuitively from the *most simple action of matrix \times vector multiplication*.

The seven Lesson Plans exemplify the role of Matrices and Linear Transformations in a *modern, fully and completely Matrix Theoretical Approach*.

It is well worth the reader's time to study the two historical lists in [44], reprinted below on pages 28 and 29 in an APPENDIX; and then try to *understand* our current *Teaching Dilemma* within our *first Linear Algebra course* and its *history*.

How would I teach a modern Linear Algebra course today ?

Given that I have recently completed this set of seven Lesson Plans that cover *all subjects* of a 'Classical' first semester *Linear Algebra Course* in 28 to 30 class days in a modern *Matrix based* way.

How would you ?

The Lesson Plans hinge on three fundamental processes :

(1) The *Row Echelon Form Reduction* allows us to *study all vector spaces*, the *intrinsic qualities* of *sets of vectors* and the *structure* of *linear vector-space relations*.

This is the subject of the first four Lesson Plans.

(2) Then *Krylov's Matrix \times Vector Iterations* [18] take over in the later Lesson Plans, when we are trying to understand the *intrinsic properties of matrices*, i.e., their *eigen structures*.

Both of these pivotal aspects of *modern Linear Algebra* rely on

(3) *Riesz' Standard Basis Matrix Representations* [23] of 1909 for *linear transformations f of n -space* that we encounter in the very first days of Lesson Plan 1.

My first semester *Lesson Plans* are *uniformly built on Matrices* and on *modern Matrix Theory and Matrix Computations*.

My Lesson Plans *do not treat determinants*, they do not touch the characteristic polynomial or polynomial root finding, nor the unstable Gram-Schmidt orthonormal basis algorithms, see Nick Trefethen and David Bau [29], p. 50, or Gauss's ill-conditioned normal equation method of 1815, see Olga Taussky [26];

nor Cramer's determinantal rule from 1750, nor the rule of signs from the 16th or 15th century, or the Ruth-Hurwitz matrix stability formulas from around 1900.

The *knowledge base of the 19th century* or of the *early 1900s* is *not sufficient* for the demands of a *modern Linear Algebra syllabus*, nor does it introduce our students to the *modern uses of Linear Algebra and Matrices*.

The two lists in the APPENDIX show the achievements of developing Linear Algebra's more *abstract notions* in centuries past and in *modern matrix computations*, – the latter only possible *after the advent of electronic computers* in World War 2.

Our students, the client disciplines and colleagues generally welcome this *switch to modernity* because such Lesson Plans develop simple *modern Matrix Theory* and *Matrix Computational notions* that are *easy to grasp, to apply, to evaluate, to retain, and easy to teach*, and just as *easy to learn interactively*.

The first class notes of my Lesson Plan 1 on pages i through v and 1 through 11 set the *tone of the class* as interactive and *accepting all inputs graciously and encouragingly from students and teachers* alike.

These first classes are best set up as *Inverse Teaching Exercises*, where *all actors have read and thought first* about the leading 16 pages of Lesson Plan 1 *by themselves* and then are *encouraged to talk about them freely* in class.

In fact, the main aim of my Lesson Plan 1 is to encourage students and teachers to contribute their thoughts and ideas freely and to gladly share their understandings and mis-understandings of mathematical notions, practices or problems, while ...

While - for example - we construct a mathematical proof of Frederic Riesz's Representation Theorem from 1909 [23] for Linear Transforms f of \mathbb{R}^n or \mathbb{C}^n in the first few days of Linear Algebra class, slowly guided from student input and coached by gentle instructors' help and advice, – (but only when needed).

This introduces the class to *Inverse Teaching* and fosters their own thoughts and deep Math Learning by following the Piaget Principle's way.

(This exercise in abstraction will help us later to study matrix representations for arbitrary bases, to understand 'basis change', and then to work with matrix eigenvalues in Lesson Plan 5 and beyond.)

But first, students have to understand how to multiply matrices and vectors, how to adhere to the "row before column" notational rule and understand the dot product of row and column vectors, and how to multiply matrices and vectors of all compatible sizes or respective 'dimensions'.

Early on, we teach students and they learn how to row reduce matrices by hand. And wonder at what happens to almost zero entries.

Students then try to create their own 'error-free' row reduction Matlab (or other software) codes. And thus they learn about the role and the effects of small, near zero pivots or of gigantic ones in Lesson Plans 2 and 3.

In Lesson Plans 4 and 5 we introduce Krylov Vector Iterations [18] to find invariant subspaces under linear transformations, see [32], and matrix eigenvectors, as well as their eigenvalues constructively – without the ballast from the 19th century of determinants, characteristic polynomials, or polynomial root finding ...

These have been *completely impractical* since *their inception* by Augustin-Louis Cauchy et al., *three centuries ago*.

Long before the advent of *electronic Computers* and before *modern Numerical Analysis* was developed, and learning for life in "*Inverse Classrooms*".

2 : Philosophical Remarks and Conclusions about the Genesis of our New Computational Results after Covid Times, a Metaphysical Outlook

Where will this desire for modernity in math all lead to ?

Where will it end?

The universe, the Earth and those who live on Earth, humans and animals, plants and clouds, climate and societies, nations and social interactions are *constantly adapting and changing* and we and they have been changing for billions of years, *forwards and back*.

The universe is continually evolving and so are we.

That is life.

Why was I tempted to write and how did I actually come to write this meta-mathematical section upon solving these old and long abandoned fundamental math and science problems?

I will now try to explain the genesis of this new interconnected and extraordinary cluster of mathematical thoughts and results from a wider perspective, if possible.

Something rarer and more special has been going on and affecting the Earth and our lives in the last couple of years.

Our minds and our individual and group consciousnesses have made leaps and bounds and we have bounced forward.

We have become *more awake spiritually*, within ourselves and of others.

We try to think '*equity and inclusion*' now.

At the same time we are *confronting our own demise*, threatened by *global epidemics*, through *overusing our resources* and by *environmental pollution*, by *needless consumption*, and affecting *our own survival* with *man-made climate change*.

In wars, started for *dubious reasons* and with *ill effects*.

And *genocide* is showing its face again around the globe.

We are still stewards of the Earth; *are we still?*

We are barely so.

How did this quite disparate research cluster come into being?

I feel that I am not, that *I was not the sole creator* here.

Besides my co-authors and colleagues and Linear Algebra's history, *some other force* was at work helping me, a *spiritual* or *karmic entity*; maybe *earthly*, but most likely *otherwise*.

It drove me on, it sustained me, it has pushed me onwards for a long time, *for 60 years* or more. This began seven decades ago in and around Köln, Germany.

In Cologne I began as a Sophomore to learn and think about how to teach at
University.

And I did *gain my first experiences* with *Interactive Teaching* of *vectors* and *matrices* in Cologne in Mai 1965, as a *newcomer* to the *subject* myself.

And this audacious approach would *follow me everywhere* I went.

As a young student of Wolfram Jehne, Roland Burlisch, Manfred Lussem, Ulrich Trottenberg at first in Cologne, and then learning from Olga Taussky, John Todd, Alston Householder, Herb Keller, Joseph Stoer, Fritz Reutter, Rolf Jeltsch, John Figgis Francis, Gene Golub, Peter Maxwell, Martin Gutknecht, Froilán Dopico, ... for many decades after; and with the help of many co-authors and of my students, and many, many others, I grew.

Linear Algebra has *challenged me* in all of my *teachings* and in much of my *research life* since; see [32, Chapter 9.1], [33], [34], [36], [44] for some of my Math and Matrix Education papers.

There was a natural, broad support for me from Dorothy, my wife; from my family, my friends, from Sepideh, Rachel and Anthony of the ILAS Education committee and all of the International Linear Algebra Society (ILAS) itself.

And last but not least, from the doctors who cured me of a deadly self-poisoning disease that affected me badly and could have killed me a couple of years ago.

I survived and am now struggling to rehabilitate myself physically, – with heartfelt thanks to those who helped me and who are still helping me along the way.

And I still feel that something is missing from this description of these extraordinary events, namely

*The spiritual force that guarded and guided me
throughout my entire life.*

Let me admit and say clearly now that I was saved by my *Angel* who would not let me die with such great tasks and joys of discovery ahead.

These tasks of Math and Math Education are now done and I am very grateful.

Now I can dedicate myself again to my other creative outlet, *photographing the world as I see it* in my inner eye, see [35] and the concluding picture of this paper for example.

And also continue with Math – on rainy days, – or when I am called to Math, and family work, – and possibly to Teaching again.

May everyone find ways to listen to his or her mentors throughout their life and stay in touch with her or his Angel – and ultimately

fulfill their karmic tasks and work on Earth.

I wish you luck and health on your journey.

What 'really' brought on this extraordinary cluster of results, all nearly at once; such questions are open to interpretation and beyond the scope of this paper — and

well beyond this author's mind.

APPENDIX

Here we list named old, ancient and modern Linear Algebra subjects that are touched upon in most of our current elementary Linear Algebra textbooks and are generally taught or touched on in our current first elementary Linear Algebra courses.

The first list below summarized the achievements from the first expansion of Linear Algebra research in the eighteen and early nineteen hundreds.

Algebra and Linear Algebra notions developed before 1930

Gaussian elimination; Gaxby, Saxby	Assur and Babylon	4000 to 2000 BE	} Standard math contents with algebraic proofs or pencil and paper explanations in a majority of our current Linear Algebra textbooks and classes today.
polynomial	Descartes	1637	
polynomial roots			
complex numbers	Cardano	1545	
rule of signs	Descartes	1637	
matrix	Leibniz, Seki	1683	
determinant	Cardano, Seki, Leibniz	1545, 1683, 1693	
Cramer's rule	Cramer	1750	
fundamental theorem of algebra	Gauss	1799	
Cauchy-Schwarz inequality	Cauchy, Schwarz	1821, 1888	
normal equation	Gauss	1822	
Ruth-Hurwitz	Ruth, Hurwitz	1876, 1895	
Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization	Gram, Schmidt	1883, 1907	
eigenvector	Euler	1751, 1760	
eigenvalue	Cauchy	1819	
characteristic polynomial	Cauchy	1819	
Cayley-Hamilton theorem	Cayley, Hamilton	1858, 1864	
Jordan normal form	Jordan	1870	
Cholesky decomposition	Cholesky	1910	
Gershgorin Circles	Gershgorin	1931	
minimal polynomial	Krylov	1931	
vector iteration	Krylov	1931	

And here is a list of modern 20th and 21st century Linear Algebra subjects.

Linear Algebra concepts and notions developed after 1930

LR factorization	historic		
Schur decomposition	Schur	1909	
Gershgorin Circles	Gershgorin	1931	} Math items less emphasized in our teachings and textbooks. 'No time left' for most of these topics.
vector iteration	Krylov	1931	
vanishing polynomial	Krylov	1931	
partial column-pivoting	Cauer	1938	
Hessenberg matrix	Hessenberg	1943	
steepest descend, Conj. Grad.	Lanzcos, Hestenes	1949	
QR factorization	(Nat. Bureau of Stand.)	1950	
Givens reflection	Givens	1950	
Householder transform	Householder	1958	
QR algorithm	Francis, Kublanovskaya	1961	
singular value decomposition	Golub, Kahan	1965	
invariant subspace theory	Watkins	1980	
SVD, 'PageRank' search engine	Page, Brin	1996	
QR multi-shift algorithm	Braman, Byers, Mathias	2002	
TensorFlow search engine	Google team	2021	

In both lists, the golden 1800s and the modern 1930 + Linear Algebra lists, the works of Semyon Aronovich Gerschgorin (1901 – 1933) [12] and Alexsei Krylov (1863 – 1945) [18] are outliers of sorts.

Gerschgorin was a professor in Leningrad and Krylov was a naval engineer and applied mathematician in Saint Petersburg at the time of their matrix results.

Incidentally, Alexsei Krylov 'presented' S. A. Gerschgorin in 1917 before the Academy of Sciences. Their respective offices were adjacent, in the same building, from two separate Universities and Departments, in this doubly named city.

Their office building was quite near to and south of the Neva River, in the joint University Sector of Leningrad and Saint Petersburg. And the Neva still flows into the Baltic Sea there.

Historic Math confluences.

In 1931 Aleksei Krylov published his seminal paper [18] on Vector Iteration and Krylov Subspaces for square matrices $A_{k,k}$. The excerpts below from Krylov's paper, translated from Russian into English, can be found at

<https://mathshistory.st-andrews.ac.uk/Biographies/KrylovAleksei/>.

"It is clear that, if for $k = 2$ and $k = 3$ it is easy to compose this [secular] equation (i.e., the characteristic polynomial $f(x)$ of a k by k matrix), then for $k = 4$ the laying-out becomes cumbersome, and for values k more than 5 this is completely unrealizable in a direct way.

Therefore one should use methods where the full development of the determinant is avoided. The aim of the paper ... is to present simple methods of composition of the secular equation (i.e., the minimal polynomial) in the developed form, after which, its solution, i.e. numerical computation of its roots, does not present any difficulty".

Krylov's first paragraph above gives a realistic description of what the majority of our students today are tasked with, when trying to compute the characteristic equation of even very low dimensional square matrices $A_{k,k}$ by hand.

In almost all of our elementary first Linear Algebra classes and in most of our textbooks, students are still asked and tasked to repeat Krylov's low size matrix dilemma today.

How cruel and fruitless.

This ill approach blocks a proper Matrix Theoretical Understanding of Matrix Eigen-structures and Matrix Eigen-behaviors.

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